

Determination of Soil Organic Carbon, B.E.C. and Certain other Soil Constituents by Soil-conductometric Method.

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Fifty Indian soils belonging to semi-desert, arid, semi-arid, sub-humid, humid-temperate and per-humid soil climatic regions have been taken to determine the specific conductance of these soils in aqueous media at 25°. These values were then correlated with the values of different soil analyzates. It has been observed that out of twenty-one soil properties only 12 soil properties viz. SiO₂ (negative), Fe₂O₃, R₂O₃, C, C/N, pH (negative), B.E.C., Exch., Ca + Mg (negative), Silt + Clay, Silt/Clay, total sand (negative) and total sand/silt + clay (negative) were found to be significantly correlated at 5% level with the specific conductance values of soils. The regression equations especially for those 'r' values (coefficients of correlation) which are significant, have only been proposed. It is suggested that the proposed reaction equations may help in the determination of a particular soil analyzate provided the corresponding specific conductivity values of soil samples are known.

THE method of soil conductivity has long been used for the determination of total soil salt contents and the nature and extent of soil alkalinity^{1,2}. However, no attempt has been made especially with Indian Soils belonging to different soil-climatic regions to study the relation of soil conductivity statistically with different soil properties. This type of work has been attempted and the results achieved have been given in this paper to get some idea about the quantitative relation of certain soil constituents in terms of soil conductance. The possibility of getting regression equations correlating specific conductance of soil with particular soil-constituents have also been seen. The proposed regression equations will prove quite helpful to determine the different soil-constituents if soil conductance of the specific soils are known and where large number of soil samples are required to be analysed for their constituents in a limited period of time.

Experimental

Fifty Indian soil samples belonging to semi-desert, arid, semi-arid, sub-humid, humid-temperate and per-humid soil-climatic regions³ have been collected and processed for our routine experiments. These soils were then analysed (Table 1) for their twenty one different soil-analyzates by the reported methods⁴.

The specific conductivity of fifty Indian soils has been measured by Ellico-Salt Bridge (Moden CM-84) operated on 230 V and 50 c/s a/c mains.

To 5 g. of each of the soil samples kept in a 100 ml. pyrex beaker, 25 ml of double distilled water were added (ratio of the soil and water, 1 : 5) and the specific conductance of the soil solution are measured at 25° with a cell constant of 0.90 with the help of the conductivity meter mentioned.

The coefficients of correlation (r) values between the specific conductivity of soils and different soil properties and their corresponding regression equations (which have only been found significant at 5% level of significance) have been given and discussed (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

The specific conductivity values of fifty natural soils have been given in Table 1 alongwith different soil properties. The co-efficients of correlation and their corresponding regression equations obtained between the specific conductivity of soils and different soil properties have been presented in Table 2. However, the corresponding regression equation of only those properties which have been found to be significant at 5% level of significance, are given and discussed.

A perusal of Table 2 clearly shows that out of twentyone soil properties only 12 of them have been significantly correlated with specific conductivity values of soils. The soil constituents viz., SiO₂ (negative), Fe₂O₃, R₂O₃, C, C/N, pH (negative), B.E.C., Exch. Ca + Mg (negative), silt + clay, silt/clay, total sand (negative) and total sand/silt + clay (Negative) have been found to be significantly correlated both at 1% and 5% level of significance. The remaining nine soil properties have not been found to be significantly correlated with the specific conductance values. It is obvious to conclude that either singly or combinedly such soil analyzates which have significant 'r' values will influence soil conductivity. Since soil is a heterogeneous system, it is not possible to explain why and how the other soil analyzates which have no significant

TABLE 2—COEFFICIENTS OF CORRELATION (r) AND REGRESSION EQUATIONS OBTAINED BETWEEN THE SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE(X) VALUES AND THE DIFFERENT SOIL PROPERTIES(Y).

Soil constituents		Co-efficients of correlation (r) values	Regression equations
SiO ₂	p.c.	-0.4694*	y = -1.98x + 83.31
Fe ₂ O ₃	"	0.4682*	y = 1.21x + 3.0
R ₂ O ₃	"	0.4292*	y = 3.97x + 12.95
Al ₂ O ₃	"	0.1667	-
CaO + MgO	"	-0.1780	-
Na ₂ O + K ₂ O	"	-0.0777	-
CaO + MgO	"	-0.1458	-
Na ₂ O + K ₂ O	"	-0.0663	-
N	"	0.4660*	y = 0.28x + 0.54
C	"	0.3009*	y = 3.17x + 10.71
C/N	"	-0.3217*	y = -0.62x + 7.51
pH	"	0.3000*	y = 2.53x + 17.87
B.E.C. meq./100g	"	-0.3545*	y = -3.13x + 14.40
Exch. Ca + Mg.	"	0.0046	-
Exch. Na + K	"	0.0335	-
Clay	"	0.3130*	y = 5.87x + 34.61
Silt + clay	"	0.4246*	y = 0.23x + 0.73
Silt/clay	"	-0.4465*	y = -51.59 + 66.14
Total sand	"	-0.2894	y = -0.37x + 2.08
Total sand	"	-0.1904	-
Silt + clay	"	-0.1820	-
SiO ₂ /R ₂ O ₃	"		
S A.R.	"		

Note : * Significant at 5% level of significance.

'r' values failed to correlate with the values of soil conductivity.

The regression equations proposed in Table 2 especially for those 'r' values which are significant may well be used for the determination of the corresponding soil analyzate values. These equations may prove useful for the determination of a particular soil analyzate value if the specific conductance value of that soil is available. This will be more true for soils belonging to the climatic regions mentioned in this work.

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